

THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPING SANOGEN REFLECTION

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Abstract. *During the theoretical and practical study of the research problem, it was found that the reflective knowledge and skills of future teachers are one of the main factors influencing the development of sanogenic thinking. This situation primarily requires a comprehensive psychological and pedagogical study and analysis of the reflection process. The personal and professional development of any individual is closely related to the reflective process. Furthermore, development is not only ensured from a professional perspective but also from a physical and intellectual standpoint.*

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Reflection (from Latin “reflexio” – turning back, reflecting) is one of the acts of human consciousness, meaning a mental process that involves the subject's awareness of their (internal) psychological feelings and states. Reflection expresses, in many ways, the ontological aspect of human life and is recognized as one of the individual's distinctive features.

M.K. Ismailov has studied reflective skills as a form of activity aimed at thinking, self-awareness, self-regulation, and understanding one's personal actions and their consequences. The researcher defines reflective skills as the main indicator of healthy thinking: “If we consider reflection as a method of reflecting a specific process as a whole, it allows us to observe this process, identify its shortcomings, and analyze them,” he states.

In pedagogical literature, two traditions in explaining reflective processes are distinguished:

The reflective analysis of consciousness leading to the explanation and construction of cognitive and emotional experiences;

The reflection of the understanding of self and interpersonal communication content.

R. Brandenburg, in an international scientific research dedicated to teachers' exchange of experiences, wrote that the function of reflection involves clarifying the impact and role of identification, as well as testing assumptions.

Reflection is the ability to describe self-awareness, understand how the subject is perceived as an interlocutor in a communication process, identify problems and their causes, and analyze and study them. The practice of reflection is emphasized as a valuable tool for teachers, noting that mastering it is a process that requires a lot of time, effort, and energy.

According to S. Katz, individual reflection is a solitary activity where the person, even if taking a critical stance, can only use their own thinking and understanding to check the actions they have observed. In contrast, collaborative reflection requires exchanging information, overcoming conflicts and disagreements, respecting individual differences, planning the educational process to meet the needs of others, and fostering trust.

By observing the process of human perception of the environment, one can identify whether their thinking is based on sanogenic (healthy) or pathogenic (unhealthy) skills. The pathogenicity of thinking is defined as a collection of negative outlooks that harm a person's health, which is manifested in emotional instability and conflicts in the process of self and interpersonal relationships.

In studying the issues of individual upbringing and teaching, sanogenic and its opposite, pathogenic reflection, is defined as follows:

Sanogenic reflection is a thinking style that reduces internal conflict, stress, and anxiety, enabling the management of negative thoughts, emotions, needs, and desires, thereby preventing diseases.

However, we believe that while these terms are closely related, they are not always used in the same sense. N.V. Pavlyuchenkova writes: "Reflection and thinking concepts are closely related. Thinking is aimed at problem-solving. If thinking, as a process, is self-oriented, this state is called 'meta-thinking' or 'reflection'".

Thinking, as an activity, is consciously organized by the subject through reflection.

People who lack developed thinking tend to have weak control over their desires and impulses, and often act instinctively, impulsively, and aggressively. They are characterized by roughness, crudeness, rudeness, and tend to be involved in numerous conflicts. These individuals are often emotional and impulsive, frequently changing jobs and having difficulty working in teams. They are typically prone to emotional reactions such as surprise, astonishment, and feeling new things, all of which contribute to the elevation of thought, ensuring enjoyment and excitement.

The truth (or falseness), correctness (or incorrectness), and adequacy (or inadequacy) of human thoughts, ideas, decisions, and conclusions are marked by the presence of confidence and doubt.

Mood, whether happy or unpleasant, as well as emotional states like euphoria and fear, influence intellectual processes and the productivity of the brain hemispheres. Therefore, emotional states directly affect the direction of thinking, either positively or negatively.

Sanogenic thinking is a healthy, supportive, and motivating thinking style, while sanogenic reflection involves using a certain algorithm to reconsider and organize personal pathogenic (unhealthy) thinking stereotypes. It is the ability to reflect on problems and difficulties that arise during a person's activities and to represent them correctly.

Thus, reflection is a universal mechanism for changing thinking and behavior strategies, but it is neutral and does not inherently possess a positive or negative nature. Whether the changes are positive or negative depends on the individual—their actions, needs, relationships, values, goals, and the degree of success or failure they experience. Positive results in reflective activity ensure its mental automation.

Researchers are united in their opinion on two main points:

First, reflection is the primary psychological mechanism for organizing educational interaction by the teacher, which allows this interaction to be described as a reflective process of managing students' educational activities.

Second, reflection is the most important professional quality that determines the teacher's professional competence, which is simultaneously carried out by the teacher.

Through reflection, knowledge becomes a style of activity. The teacher begins by superficially understanding their actions and gradually deepens the analysis: they search for cause-and-effect relationships and evaluate the results of their activities.

Pedagogical reflection is primarily related to the organizational and activity domain (what the teacher has done, how they organized their actions, the environment, and the students). Teachers are offered external action reflection for self-assessment. However, in the activities of teachers, thinking, motivation, emotions, and self-awareness are considered relatively more important than external actions.

Sanogenic reflection leads to a reduction in the suffering caused by negative emotions such as failure, blame, frustration, and fear under the influence of emotionally charged situations.

The function of sanogenic reflection is to objectify and correct non-constructive mental automatisms. This function determines the opportunity to influence the development of the emotional competence components. By developing sanogenic reflection, one achieves sanogenic thinking.

When the concept of sanogenic thinking is analyzed from a pedagogical perspective, it is based on the thesis of the cognitive evaluation's priority in relation to the pedagogical problems and emotional experiences that arise in the context of the educational process. This means the student uses their thoughts to influence emotions and, by changing cognitive evaluations, learns constructive methods of resolving pedagogical problems related to their activities.

Sanogenic thinking allows the focus and identification (clarification) of cognitive processes. A student who masters sanogenic thinking skills will be able to control their negative thoughts, protect themselves from them, and acquire knowledge for constructively resolving problematic situations.

The essence of sanogenic thinking is the constructive revision of previous experiences. It involves identifying ineffective reflective strategies that lead to various negative situations and correcting or abandoning them in favor of optimal strategies, aiming to reduce negative emotional charges. These strategies are unscientific and serve as philosophies in everyday life.

The development of sanogenic reflection helps reduce anxiety, panic, and negative emotions (such as frustration, fear of failure, guilt, etc.), optimize character traits, and increase the internal quality and effectiveness of educational activities.

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